

halide and the sulphate ion-pairs of complexed cobalt(III).

TABLE 4—log ASSOCIATION CONSTANT (log β) AT 25°

[Co(NH ₃) ₆] ³⁺ .Z ⁻		[Co(en) ₃] ³⁺ .Z ⁻	
Z ⁻	log β	Z ⁻	log β
Cl ⁻	1.48 ^a	Cl ⁻	1.72 ^a
	1.87 ^b		0.99 ^c
	0.96 ^c		
Br ⁻	1.50 ^d	Br ⁻	1.32 ^b
	1.66 ^b		
	0.96 ^c		
I ⁻	1.77 ^e	SO ₄ ²⁻	3.10 ^c
	1.77 ^f		2.98 ^g
	-0.40 ^h		
SO ₄ ²⁻	3.56 ^a		
	3.26 ^c		
	3.50 ^b		

^aRef. 1. ^bRef. 2. ^cRef. 4. ^dRef. 5. ^eRef. 17. ^fRef. 18. ^gRef. 19. ^hRef. 20. ⁱRef. 7.

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Mechanism of Ruthenium(III) Chloride catalysed Oxidation of Glycollic Acid and Ethanol by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

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RUTHENIUM compounds are very important from the technological point of view¹. Oxidation of diols in alkaline solution by sodium hypochlorite using ruthenium(III) chloride catalyst gives extensive carbon bond cleavage². Oxidation of glycols³ and cycloalcohols⁴ has been reported from our laboratory. In the present study oxidation of glycollic acid and ethanol by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) using ruthenium(III) chloride as a homogeneous catalyst has been undertaken to see how the change in the reactive group in organic substrate, keeping the number of carbon atoms same, effects the reaction kinetics and whether ruthenium(III) chloride catalyses the oxidation of organic compounds having different reactive groups by hydride ion transfer only or the charge transfer process is also there.

Experimental

Glycollic acid (Riedel) and ethanol (B.D.H.) were used as such. Hexacyanoferrate(III) (AnalaR) was dissolved in the double-distilled water. Ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson Matthey) was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and the final strengths of the acid and the catalyst were 3.342×10^{-3} and 2.74×10^{-2} M respectively. All other chemicals used were either AnalaR or chemically pure grade.

The progress of the reaction was measured at different intervals of time by estimating the hexacyanoferrate(II) produced by titrating it against a standard solution of ceric sulphate using ferroin as a redox indicator. Temperature of the reaction was kept constant by keeping the reaction mixture into an electrically operated thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).

Results and Discussion

Ruthenium(III) chloride catalysed oxidation of glycollic acid and ethanol by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) was studied under the conditions where the uncatalysed reaction was negligible. Ionic strength of the medium was kept constant with the help of a standard solution of potassium chloride although the change in the ionic strength of the medium does not affect the reaction velocity. In the kinetic measurements rate of the reaction is given in terms of the dc/dt values obtained from the initial slopes of the zero order plots and are shown in the terms of remaining hexacyanoferrate(III) concentrations per minute.

It was observed that $-dc/dt$ values as well as the zero order rate constant (k_s) values remain constant showing zero order kinetics with respect to hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration. A slight increase in the rate values calculated from the initial slopes of the zero order plots at higher hexacyanoferrate(III) concentrations was observed which might be due to the further oxidation of the intermediate products via the uncatalysed route. Its further proof comes from the zero order plots where zero order rate constant values begin to increase after a certain stage of the reaction. Moreover it has been reported that the intermediate product is further oxidised only with alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) and ruthenium(III) chloride does not participate in the reaction⁵. It was observed that the rate of the reaction shows direct proportionality with respect to organic substrate at its low concentrations which tends to become zero order at higher concentrations of the substrate. A steady increase in k_s as well as $-dc/dt$ values with increasing concentration of ruthenium(III) chloride was observed which shows that the order of the reaction with respect to ruthenium(III) chloride is unity. Constant values of the reaction velocity constant (k_1) further confirm this nature. It was observed that $-dc/dt$ values decrease with increasing hydroxide ion concentrations indicating that hydroxide ions have a retarding effect on the reaction velocity.

To study the effect of temperature on the reaction rate and to determine different thermodynamic parameters the reaction was studied at four different temperatures at constant concentrations of all the reactants. The values of different thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 1. These values clearly show that energy of activation in

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC DATA

Compd.	ΔE^\ddagger kcal g mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger e. u.	Δ^\ddagger kcal g mol ⁻¹
Glycollic acid	14.37	-57.33	31.74
Ethanol	12.11	-60.76	30.52

case of ethanol is comparatively low indicating easier formation of the activated complex in case of ethanol. These values also suggest that similar mechanism is operative for both the substrates.

After the completion of the reaction, the final oxidation products were identified with the help of paper chromatography technique as well as by the spot test methods⁶. The final oxidation products in the case of glycollic acid and ethanol were found to be oxalic acid and acetic acid respectively. Rate of the reaction in two different substrates was found to be in the order, ethanol > glycollic acid, which is supported by the lower value of energy of activation in the former case. This shows that ruthenium(III) chloride catalyses the oxidation of alcoholic group quickly as compared to the carboxylic group. From the experi-

mental results it becomes apparent that for one molecule of ethanol or glycollic acid four molecules of hexacyanoferrate(III) are consumed. Thus the actual amount of acid produced in case of both the substrates in a particular run will be one-fourth of the initial hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration and the stoichiometry of the reactions may be given as

and

Electronic spectral studies have confirmed that ruthenium(III) chloride exists⁷ in the hydrated form as $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$. Metal ions of the form $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ are also known to exist as $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})]^{2+}$ in alkaline medium⁸. In the present study it is quite probable that the species $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})]^{2+}$ might assume the general form $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{6-x}(\text{OH})_x]^{(3-x)+}$. The value of x would always be less than six because the existence of hexahydroxy species is not certain⁹. Thus this might be considered as the only reactive species of ruthenium(III) in alkaline medium. Our kinetic data clearly show that soluble ruthenium(III) species exist in the alkaline medium with at least one hydroxide ion in its coordination. The continuous decrease in reaction velocity with increasing $[\text{OH}^-]$ indicates that more and more $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ is converted into $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})]^{2+}$.

On the basis of the experimental results the final rate law in terms of decreasing concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III) comes out to be

$$V_1 = -\frac{d[\text{Fey}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1k_2[\text{S}][\text{Ru}^{III}]_T}{k_2 + k_1[\text{S}] + k_{-1}[\text{OH}^-]}$$

where $[\text{Fey}] = [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$, $[\text{S}]$ = concentration of organic substrate and k_1 , k_2 and k_{-1} are the rate constants. This equation clearly explains the observed direct proportionality of the reaction rate with respect to ruthenium(III) chloride concentrations. Nature shown by the substrate and reverse proportionality shown by the hydroxide ions is also quite clear.

Further verification of this rate law might be made by reversing the equation. It was observed that the plots $1/V_1$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $1/V_1$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$ give straight lines with positive intercepts which itself confirms the rate law. Moreover k_1 , k_2 and k_{-1} values, calculated with the help of intercepts and slopes of the plots, further confirm the rate law and the proposed mechanism.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Threonine and Methionine by *N,N*-Dichlorotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide in Water - Methanol Medium in Presence of Perchloric Acid

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ALTHOUGH extensive studies have been reported on the kinetics and mechanisms of oxidation of a variety of substrates by monohalosulphonamides like *N*-chloro- and *N*-bromobenzene or toluenesulphonamides^{1,2}, studies by dihalosulphonamides have recently been initiated in our laboratories³⁻⁴. As a part of these investigations, we report herein the kinetics of oxidation of two amino acids, namely, threonine and methionine by *N,N*-dichlorotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide in 1:1 (v/v) water-methanol medium in the presence of perchloric acid.

Experimental

N,N-Dichlorotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide, abbreviated as dichloramine-T (DCT), was prepared by the reported method⁵. The stock solution (~ 0.05 mol dm⁻³) of the oxidant in pure methanol was prepared and standardised by iodometric method and preserved in amber-coloured bottles. Chromatographically pure amino acids (SISCO, India), threonine (Thr) and methionine (Met) were further assayed by acetous perchloric acid method⁶. Aqueous stock solutions (~ 0.1 mol dm⁻³) of the amino acids (AA) were prepared in double-distilled water. Preliminary investigations of the reactions showed that the variations in ionic strength of the

medium had no significant effect on the rates of oxidations. All other reagents used were of accepted grades of purity.

Kinetic measurements: Kinetic studies were made in glass-stoppered pyrex boiling tubes under pseudo-first order conditions with [AA] >> [DCT]. The reactions were initiated by the quick addition of measured amounts of oxidant solution (0.0005-0.004 mol dm⁻³) thermostated at the desired temperature to solutions containing required amounts of amino acid (0.005-0.10 mol dm⁻³), perchloric acid (0.0002-0.30 mol dm⁻³), methanol and water (to maintain 1:1, v/v water-methanol composition), pre-equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions was monitored for two half-lives by iodometric estimation of unreacted oxidant at regular time intervals. The pseudo-first order rate constants (*k*_{obs}) were calculated by the graphical methods and the values were reproducible within ± 4% error.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometries of DCT- amino acid reactions were determined in 1:1 (v/v) water-methanol medium in the presence of varying concentrations of perchloric acid (0.0002-0.30 mol dm⁻³) by equilibrating varying ratios of [DCT]₀ to [AA]₀ at room temperature for different intervals of time. The products were found to be CO₂, ammonia and the corresponding aldehyde analysed by standard tests⁷. Toluene-*p*-sulphonamide, the reduced product of DCT, was detected by paper chromatography. The observed stoichiometries may be represented by equations (1) and (2).

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of threonine and methionine by dichloramine-T in 1:1 (v/v) water-methanol medium were studied under varying conditions. The results are shown in Tables 1 and 2 and Fig 1. At fixed [AA]₀ and [HClO₄], the plots of log [DCT]₀/[DCT] vs time were linear at least for two half-lives (Fig. not shown) and the pseudo-first order constants computed from the plots were insensitive to the variations in [DCT]₀, establishing first order kinetics in [DCT] for both the oxidations. At constant [DCT] and [HClO₄], the rate increased with increase in [Thr] with a fractional order dependence (~0.6) while the rate was independent of [Met] (Table 1). The rate decreased with increase in [H⁺] for the oxidation with an inverse fractional order (-0.6) dependence. But the rate increased with increase in [H⁺] for Met oxidation with a first order dependence (Table 1). Variations in ionic